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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 17

Issue 5

Pages: 453-460

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1577

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10695448

Manuscript Accepted: 01-31-2024

Entrepreneurial Orientation, Product Innovation, and Differentiation Strategies as Predictors of Organizational Performance of Small Coffee Shops in Parañaque City

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Abstract

Research has been done in Parañaque City on the relationship between organizational performance and entrepreneurial orientation, product innovation, and differentiation strategies. The purpose of this study was to identify potential strategies for creating small-business owners of successful coffee shops who could continue to provide high-quality goods and services. Based on a representative sample of 153 micro entrepreneurs aged 20 to 41 and above, an indication was obtained from the small coffee shop entrepreneurs' survey. Based on the entrepreneur's personal and business profile, the researcher used multiple linear regression technique to identify changes pertaining to business and small coffee shop entrepreneurs in terms of demographic features, entrepreneurial orientation, product innovation, and differentiation strategies, use of resources, organizational structure, and organizational performance. The findings demonstrated the empowerment of small coffee shop owners in Parañaque City, as evidenced by the independent variable of entrepreneurial orientation, the dependent variables of organizational performance and the entrepreneur's individual business profile, and the mediating variables of product innovation and differentiation strategies.

Keywords: *entrepreneurial orientation, product innovation, differentiation strategies, and organizational performance*

Introduction

Nowadays coffee business is changing and becoming more global, Coffee is a popular crop among entrepreneurs (Daufina, D. et. al., 2019). The nation that produced coffee was unstable and constantly shifting. Due to ongoing knowledge and advancement, the coffee business was reinvented, and coffee got more specialized. In their daily routines, every Filipino has partnered with coffee. Coffee shops serve as more than simply places to quench your thirst—they can also be used as restaurants, internet cafes, hangout spots, places to watch football, and information hubs (Irma, A. et. al., 2020). Small coffee shops began opening shop in Parañaque City at that time to offer coffee goods with superior health benefits for the body. The feeling of personal ownership or connection to the coffee shop that the customer chooses should be addressed in addition to the consumer feelings of arousal and pleasure, given the growing number of customers who attend coffee shops to study or do business (Hwang, J. et. al., 2021). Given the fierce rivalry in the food and beverage industry, which forces companies to continuously improve creativity and innovation in order to remain in business, operating a coffee shop demands solid planning in order to survive (Rahardjo, B., et. al., 2019) Compared to other small coffee shops, innovative and strategic coffee items and small coffee shops needed further refinement.

The establishment of small coffee shops aimed to achieve organizational success, with innovation serving as a contingency plan. Employers that are properly and successfully run can take advantage of their highly skilled and creative workforce to achieve optimal performance through innovation (McDowell, W. C., et. al., 2018). SMEs must be as creative and proactive as possible to enable their best navigation and increased production in whatever business environments they operate in. Additionally, they ought to promote more purposefully spontaneous acts that have the power to effect change, boost productivity, enhance organizational effectiveness, and provide an edge over competitors. If a company wishes to rule its specialized market, it must consistently apply a differentiation strategy. In order to compete in a market where there is competition, managers employ differentiation and cost leadership tactics. Nevertheless, they should also prioritize innovation because it serves as a vital link between competitive strategies and company performance (Bayraktar, C. A., et. al., 2017). Small-scale coffee shops in Parañaque City would gain from entrepreneurs' creative product development. To boost corporate earnings, client numbers, and sales statistics, MSME players should further enhance their product innovation, both through new technical innovations and innovations in the creation and development of new items (Faerrosa, L., et. al., 2022). A company's ability to accurately respond to client demands and complaints about product quality, customer wants, expanding into new areas, and product innovation can be viewed as a sustainable competitive advantage (Kuncoro, W. and Suriani, W., 2018.) It was consequently necessary for small coffee shops to have unique perspectives, concepts, and innovative products. In order to differentiate themselves from competitors and win market share, entrepreneurs often created innovative new items.

The fast-paced growth of Parañaque City and the ensuing heightened competitiveness for small enterprises have led to a noticeable shift in the small coffee shop industry.

In order to remain competitive, entrepreneurs needed to enhance their adaptability skills. Small and medium-sized coffee shops must use the entrepreneurial orientation business plan to enhance their customer service performance (Ardhi, M. K., & Mulyo, J. H. (2021). Information about the market and competitors that emerges in the outside world can serve as a basis for marketing initiatives and entrepreneurial training, both of which can ultimately improve the performance of businesses (Yaskun, M., et. al., (2023). More product innovation would be the result of an effective entrepreneurial orientation for entrepreneurs.

Many entrepreneurs have investigated the effect of an entrepreneurial mindset on organizational performance by utilizing a variety of moderating factors. Nonetheless, a variety of non-uniform moderating factors are still employed to show how an entrepreneurial attitude influences organizational performance. The relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and the significance of new goods is moderated by the corporate life cycle, suggesting that the stage of a company's life cycle will influence how quickly its entrepreneurial orientation effects the originality of new products (Yi, H., Amenuvor, F., and Boateng, H., 2021). The study's e-commerce adoption model, market orientation, and entrepreneurial orientation will benefit managerial and academic facets (Sriyudha, Y., et al., 2020).

The conduct of an entrepreneur is characterized by their ability to identify new markets, satisfy clients, outperform rivals in seizing business opportunities, and take calculated risks (Wahyuni, N., and Sara, I., 2020). Strategic management, which plays a significant role in identifying and utilizing the resources and capabilities required to gain a competitive advantage, tends to enhance the application of sustainable entrepreneurial orientation in the convergence of the disciplines of strategy, entrepreneurship, and sustainability (Criado-Gomis, A., et al., 2020). Research on determining organizational effectiveness through an entrepreneurial mindset was piqued. However, it has been noted that there is a research gap regarding the use of moderating variables on the influence of entrepreneurial attitude as a detector of organizational success. the absence of consistent use of differentiation methods and product innovation while pursuing an entrepreneurial attitude. Therefore, the purpose of the study is to assess entrepreneurial orientation, product innovation, and differentiation tactics among Paranaque City's small coffee shops as markers of organizational performance.

Literature Review

Entrepreneurial Orientation

Another way to think of entrepreneurial orientation is as a business orientation with values on initiatives to recognize and seize opportunities (Fachrozic, S. V., et al., 2022). It was also stated that companies with a strong entrepreneurial orientation would be more open to taking risks rather than merely depending on their past survival strategies. Risk-taking has both a financial and a social component. In addition to proactiveness and inventiveness, we find that collaboration is a crucial component of social entrepreneurial orientation (Lurtz, K., & Kreutzer, K., 2017). An entrepreneurial-oriented small coffee shop owner would want to launch new businesses by taking risks and embracing uncertainty in order to turn a profit and expand by identifying possibilities and assembling the necessary resources. The entrepreneurial orientation of a small coffee shop is a procedure carried out in an effort to compete with other businesses. The process of developing entrepreneurial strategies that business owners employ to establish objectives, uphold their vision, and gain a competitive edge is known as entrepreneurial orientation. (Hamdana, H.; Sopiah, S.; Pratikto, H., 2021). The entrepreneurial focus of tiny coffee shops played a significant role in their performance, particularly in the face of uncertain economic situations. Effectiveness, sales growth, and operational efficiency are only a few of the SMEs' performance metrics that are highly correlated with entrepreneurial approach (Small, E., 2018). The term "entrepreneurial orientation" refers to an organization's decision-making process, conduct, and outlook on the market. It also describes an organization's proactive approach to incorporating environmentally friendly practices into its daily operations (Mostepaniuk, A., et al., 2022).

Product Innovation

Small coffee shops developed their innovative skills via competency, teamwork, and skill knowledge. Small coffee shops used a variety of inventive methods to make their new goods. Innovation has its strategic uses, giving small coffee businesses a competitive edge and flexible operations. Small coffee shop owners learned about international business techniques and money management. Small coffee shop owners have also found success with cutting-edge agricultural and technological products. In order to establish a strong organizational commitment, small coffee businesses used a powerful management function. The company innovates a lot in both its products and processes because it thinks that doing so will help it decommoditize its goods and raise their price, while doing so will reduce its production costs (Chaochotechuang, P., et al., 2019). Small-business owners of coffee shops started implementing value chains in tandem with regular webinars and guidance from government agencies. Together, planning and managing also made it possible for small-business owners of coffee shops to introduce successful new products. Shoes SMEs' owners and managers should focus more on the market so that their company can develop innovative products that suit its needs. According to Tarigan (2018), small coffee shop entrepreneurs' leadership has led to enhanced organizational performance, which is one of the positive results of product innovation.

Differentiation Strategies

Owners and operators of small coffee shops have used differentiation strategies to provide their customers with the best coffee features and goods. Depending on their unique entrepreneurial circumstances, small retailing enterprises appear to need to pursue differentiation

strategy either in isolation or in conjunction with cost leadership (Linton, G., & Kask, J., 2017). Positional advantage somewhat moderates the association between differentiation strategy and export performance, and differentiation strategies have a beneficial impact on SMEs' export performance. E. Navaia et al. (2023). It was highlighted that the performance of manufacturing organizations is based on their capacity for adaptability in strategic planning and for combining industrial and internal setting elements when developing differentiation strategies. Islami, X., and associates, (2020). From a cultural standpoint, coffee shops have developed into a hub and ideal setting for social contact, offering individuals a place to gather, converse, write, read, or simply spend the time—whether alone or with others (Suarez, A. N., et al., 2017). Coffee shops are well-known for using aroma marketing in addition to the restaurant business to boost sales. N. A. Latina et al. (2022). Instead of producing and distributing commodities, high perceived value businesses or those that employ differentiation strategies move up the value ladder through branding, product sorting, cleaning and packing, industrial processing, innovation, certifications, distribution, and/or direct sales. Some of these businesses even own stores (Brenes, E. R., et al., 2020). On the other hand, mainstream businesses and brand owners are under growing pressure from stakeholders to implement sustainability policies in order to lower risks and boost competitiveness. This is because a third of all companies have adopted sustainability strategies, and the most innovative actors have embraced new differentiation strategies like direct trade and transparency (Bager, S. L., & Lambin, E. F., 2020). The company's capacity to quickly develop unique products and services will improve the hotel's efficacy and efficiency, which will raise overall sales and revenue (Semuel, H., et al., 2017).

Micro, Small, Medium Enterprises (MSME)

Employment and asset are the two criteria used by PSA (2020) to define MSMEs. Micro enterprises are defined as having fewer than ten employees, small enterprises as having between 10 and 99 employees, and medium firms as having between 100 and 199 employees. In the National Capital Region, there will be 201,123 MSMEs overall in 2020. A shift in behavior for online business events was brought about by the new normal. A variety of MSMEs in Paranaque City realized that in order to produce predictors of organizational performance, the new normal would require an entrepreneurial attitude, product innovation, and differentiation strategy. The Covid-19 pandemic significantly affected business operations worldwide, especially for MSMEs. When the pandemic struck, the quick response included implementing the enhanced community quarantine (ECQ), which provided aid to the affected families and businesses. There were enormous financial losses as a result of the pandemic. MSMEs were impacted by the plan for a shutdown and quarantine during a pandemic.

99.56% of all businesses are Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSMEs) (Cammayo, E. and Perez, E., 2021). The organizational performance of MSMEs was evaluated based on their strategies and operations. The entrepreneurial company had an impact on the Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises' (MSMEs) financial situation. Product innovation and MSMEs' entrepreneurial inclination have been connected, and this will affect the company's organizational success. Micro, small, and medium enterprise (MSMEs) firms were structured by the entrepreneurs through a strategy of product innovation and differentiation, which allowed them to prosper.

Organizational Performance of Small Coffee Shops in Paranaque City

As per PSA (2021), small businesses are defined as those that employ 10 to 99 people and have an asset size of more than ₱3 million but less than ₱15 million. In the Philippines, tiny coffee shops served as global ambassadors for innovative commercial products. Given that millennials make up the majority of coffee shop patrons, entrepreneurs hoping to open their own stores may choose to focus on the tastes and aversions of young adults when it comes to coffee shops (Suarez, A. et al., 2017). Product innovation in the Philippines was assessed in relation to challenges, efficacy, and the goals and perseverance of Filipino entrepreneurs. Thanks to the efforts of company owners, law enforcement officers, professionals, and other reliable institutions, small coffee shops have been found and made known. Small coffee shops have realized how important entrepreneurs are to the development of their distinct strategy, innovative products, and entrepreneurial mindset. Coffee shops are well-known for using aroma marketing in addition to the restaurant business to boost sales (Latina, N. et al., 2022). The success of small coffee firms was correlated with their entrepreneurial performance. In order to create coffee shops and cafés that strengthen community ties, research, theory, and real-world applications are combined in the process of "designing for community" (Waxman, L., 2022). The adoption and promotion of novel products are greatly influenced by small coffee shop owners. Innovative products have been created by small coffee shops through the use of organizational value creation, entrepreneurial thinking, and managerial techniques.

Methodology

This quantitative research study uses a thorough survey that small coffee shop owners in Paranaque City answered in order to gather strong data and an understanding of the motivations and methods used by entrepreneurs to achieve their entrepreneurial orientation.

In order to achieve this goal, the researcher employed a descriptive strategy in this research study. The descriptive approach focuses on the ideas or circumstances that already exist. The objective is to gather data and facts from the interviewees in order to identify and evaluate the behaviors that will enable entrepreneurs to be inspired in order to develop and produce new, profitable goods in Paranaque City. This type of study uses a descriptive design and is frequently conducted and reported using survey questions.

Results

This section covers the data presentation, analysis, and interpretation as well as the outcomes of the statistical procedures used in the investigation.

<i>Innovativeness</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Our coffee shop uses unique practices and this enables attainment of an impressive overall performance.	3.93	Effective
Our coffee shop improves practices that showcase an excellent innovative performance.	3.94	Effective
Our coffee shop has the latest information on practices that shows achievement of a unique performance.	3.95	Effective
Grand Mean:	3.94	Effective
Proactiveness		
Our coffee shop responds more quickly to changes in the environment compared to other coffee shops that shows active performance.	3.94	Effective
Our coffee shop adopts new practices on coffee business in our business location that upbeats an overall performance.	3.95	Effective
Our coffee shop constantly looks out for new ways of doing things which requires hands-on approach and this leads to a remarkable performance.	3.95	Effective
Grand Mean:	3.95	Effective
Risk-Taking		
Our coffee shop prefers to try new procedures than sticking to the existing one and this qualifies an accomplishment of a total performance.	3.96	Effective
With the current challenging environment of coffee industry, our coffee shop prefers additional investment to product innovation that shows flexibility of our total performance.	3.97	Effective
Our coffee shop is always ready to try new practices that shows innovation of our inclusive performance.	3.97	Effective
Grand Mean:	3.97	Effective
Architectural Innovation		
Our coffee shop prefers creating designs according to customer preferences to enable customer relationship resulting to innovative performance.	3.99	Effective
Our coffee shop always gives loyalty discounts to our customers to showcase innovative performance of our business procedures.	3.87	Effective
Our coffee shop prefers new technology to showcase innovative performance of the company.	4.00	Effective
Grand Mean:	3.95	Effective
Incremental Innovation		
Our coffee shop always develops existing products and this allows continuous improvement of an overall performance.	3.95	Effective
Our coffee shop prefers adding features to existing coffee products and this allows fulfillment of a total performance.	3.95	Effective
Our coffee shop prefers bringing something new in product and trends for our customers and this enables an innovational performance.	3.95	Effective
Grand Mean:	3.95	Effective
Disruptive Innovation		
Our coffee shop prefers discovering unique products and this showcase an innovative performance.	3.96	Effective
Our coffee shop always creates unique products and this generates revenue as part of an overall performance.	3.96	Effective
Our coffee shop prefers to adapt new innovations as an overall performance achievement.	3.97	Effective
Grand Mean:	3.96	Effective
Product Differentiation		
Our coffee shop usually flavors our coffee products according to the personal choice or preference of our customers that showcase strategic performance achievement.	3.93	Effective
Our coffee shop prefers our own version of coffee products and this enables an achievement a notable differentiated performance.	3.93	Effective
Our coffee shop always gives affordable and best quality product and this allows an attainment of an impressive differential strategic performance.	3.97	Effective
Grand Mean:	3.95	Effective
Cost Leadership		
Our coffee shop always give promo for special events and this enables quality performance strategy.	3.99	Effective
Our coffee shop prefers giving discount cards and this shows strategic overall performance.	3.97	Effective
Our coffee shop prefers to focus on standardized products as part of our strategic organizational performance.	3.97	Effective
Grand Mean:	3.98	Effective
Focus		

Our coffee shop prefers variety of coffee products and this enables differentiation strategy of an inspiring overall performance.	3.96	Effective
Our coffee shop always thinks of discovering related products that showcase strategic difference of an impressive total performance.	3.96	Effective
Our coffee shop value innovation in differentiating our product features that indicates strategic performance.	3.96	Effective
Grand Mean:	3.96	Effective

Discussion

1. Assessment of the Effectiveness of Entrepreneurial Orientation, Product Innovation, and Differentiation Strategies as Predictors of Organizational Performance of Small Coffee Shops in Parañaque City

In terms of innovativeness, “Our coffee shop has the latest information on practices that shows achievement of a unique performance” received the highest mean of 3.95 (Effective) and ““Our coffee shop uses unique practices, and this enables attainment of an impressive overall performance” with the lowest weighted mean of 3.93 (Effective). In terms of proactiveness, “Our coffee shop adopts new practices on coffee business in our business location that upbeats an overall performance” and “Our coffee shop constantly looks out for new ways of doing things which requires hands-on approach and this leads to a remarkable performance” both got 3.95 and “Our coffee shop responds more quickly to changes in the environment compared to other coffee shops that shows active performance” with 3.94. In terms of risk-taking, “With the current challenging environment of coffee industry, our coffee shop prefers additional investment to product innovation that shows flexibility of our total performance” and “Our coffee shop is always ready to try new practices that shows innovation of our inclusive performance” both with 3.97 and “Our coffee shop prefers to try new procedures than sticking to the existing one and this qualifies an accomplishment of a total performance” with 3.96. In terms of architectural innovation, “Our coffee shop prefers new technology to showcase innovative performance of the company” got 4.0 and “Our coffee shop always gives loyalty discounts to our customers to showcase innovative performance of our business procedures” with 3.87. In terms of radical innovation, “Our coffee shop uses online app service that showcase excellent performance” got 3.89 and “Our coffee shop prefers drive thru service, and this enables an achievement of better delivery performance” with 1.01. In terms of incremental innovation, “Our coffee shop always develops existing products, and this allows continuous improvement of an overall performance”, “Our coffee shop prefers adding features to existing coffee products and this allows fulfillment of a total performance”, and “Our coffee shop prefers bringing something new in product and trends for our customers and this enables an innovational performance” all got 3.95. In terms of disruptive innovation, “Our coffee shop prefers to adapt new innovations as an overall performance achievement” got 3.97 and “Our coffee shop prefers discovering unique products and this showcase an innovative performance” and “Our coffee shop always creates unique products, and this generates revenue as part of an overall performance” with 3.96. In terms of product differentiation, “Our coffee shop always gives affordable and best quality product and this allows an attainment of an impressive differential strategic performance” got 3.97 and “Our coffee shop usually flavors our coffee products according to the personal choice or preference of our customers that showcase strategic performance achievement” and “Our coffee shop prefers our own version of coffee products and this enables an achievement a notable differentiated performance” with 3.93.

In terms of cost-leadership, “Our coffee shop always give promo for special events, and this enables quality performance strategy” got 3.99 and “Our coffee shop prefers giving discount cards and this shows strategic overall performance” and “Our coffee shop prefers to focus on standardized products as part of our strategic organizational performance” with 3.97. In terms of focus, “Our coffee shop prefers variety of coffee products, and this enables differentiation strategy of an inspiring overall performance”, “Our coffee shop always thinks of discovering related products that showcase strategic difference of an impressive total performance”, and “Our coffee shop value innovation in differentiating our product features that indicates strategic performance “all got 3.96.

2. Level of Organizational Performance of Small Coffee Shops in Parañaque City

In terms of actual achievements against set goals, “Innovative products and competitive price increased the sales of our coffee shop” obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.08 and “Creative product features and new technology in operations increased the sales of our coffee shop” obtained the lowest mean of 3.89. In terms of efficiency of business functions, areas, and processes, “Innovative products and competitive price helped in achieving the goals of our coffee shop” 4.10 and “Creative product features and new technology in operations helped in achieving the goals of our coffee shop” with 3.90. In terms of expenditures against returns, “Innovative products and competitive price resulted to an acceptable return on investment of our coffee shop” got 4.12 and “Creative product features and new technology in operations resulted to a favorable return on investment of our coffee shop” and “Differentiated products and strategic services resulted to a higher return on investment of our coffee shop” both with 3.92.

3. Test for Significant Relationship between the Assessed Level of Effectiveness of the Predictor Variables and Organizational Performance of Small Coffee Shops in Parañaque City

There were strong positive significant relationships that existed between the focus and actual achievements against set goals ($r=0.936$); between the focus and efficiency of business functions, areas, and processes ($r=0.909$); and between focus and expenditures against

returns ($r=0.897$).

A moderate positive significant relationship existed between radical innovation and actual achievements against set goals ($r=0.720$); between radical innovation and business functions, areas, and processes ($r=0.714$); and between radical innovation and expenditures against returns ($r=0.721$).

Proactiveness and incremental innovation had the same strong positive significant relationship that existed with actual achievements against set goals ($r=0.853$); proactiveness and disruptiveness with efficiency of business functions, areas, and processes ($r=0.850$); and proactiveness and risk-taking with expenditures against returns.

4. The Significant Relationship Between Organizational Performance and the Personal and Business Profile of the Respondents.

There were positive significant relationships that existed between the sex and actual achievements against set goals ($r=0.119$); between the sex and efficiency of business functions, areas, and processes ($r=0.126$); and between sex and expenditures against returns ($r=0.130$).

A negative significant relationship existed between number of years in operation and actual achievements against set goals ($r=-0.721$); between number of employees and efficiency of business functions, areas, and processes ($r=-0.137$); and between number of employees and expenditures against returns ($r=-0.141$).

Civil status and highest educational attainment had the same negative significant relationship that existed with efficiency of business functions, areas, and processes ($r=-0.090$); proactiveness and disruptiveness with efficiency of business functions, areas, and processes ($r=0.850$); and proactiveness and risk-taking with expenditures against returns.

Conclusion

Based on the foregoing findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

(1) Respondents rated entrepreneurial orientation, product innovation, and differentiation strategies as predictors of organizational performance of small coffee shops in Paranaque City as effective. (2) Respondents rated the level of organizational performance of small coffee shops in Paranaque City as effective. (3) There were significant relationships in predictor variables and organizational performance in terms of actual achievements against set goals, efficiency of business functions, areas, and processes, and expenditures against returns. The respondents' perceptions disagreed that there were significant relationships in predictor variable in terms of entrepreneurial orientation, product innovation, and differentiation strategies. (4) There were significant relationships in the personal and business profile of the respondents and organizational performance in terms of actual achievements against set goals, efficiency of business functions, areas, and processes, and expenditures against returns. The respondents' perceptions disagreed that there were significant relationships in predictor variable in terms of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, capitalization, type of organization ownership, number of years in operation, and number of employees.

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions, the researcher submits the following recommendations:

(1) Small coffee shops in Paranaque City ought to be enthusiastic to learn how to be entrepreneurial-oriented through rearranging the operational procedures and practices that would reach customers. Small coffee shops in Paranaque City should constantly develop differentiating strategies by investigating how each entrepreneur has innovated their product with a focus on enthusiasm and curiosity. Small coffee shops in Paranaque City should constantly develop differentiating strategies by investigating how each entrepreneur has innovated their product with a focus on enthusiasm and curiosity. Small coffee shops in Paranaque City need to be creative with their product branding and packaging in order to match their menu designs. As part of their marketing expansion, small coffee shops in Paranaque City could set up an internet store for convenient drive-thru systems. Using digital marketing techniques like social media, mobile applications, and web content, small coffee shops in Paranaque City must restructure their operations to be open around-the-clock for customers. Small coffee shops in Paranaque City ought to implement a loyalty program that rewards regular customers who are avid coffee drinkers. The foundation of a successful small business is a loyal following of coffee enthusiasts. Small coffee shops in Paranaque City should conduct market research before planning and introducing their novel items. To be ready for any changes they may meet in the new normal set up of business, small coffee shops must record, cover, and report the capabilities and capacities of their novel product and service. With the aid of technology, little coffee shops in Paranaque City should learn to adjust to customer behavior. (2) Small coffee businesses in Paranaque City should find suitable distributors that share their goals and objectives. The business goal of small coffee shops in Paranaque City should include learning to experiment with new technology. In Paranaque City, small coffee shops must create a business method or a strategic roadmap and circulate it with your stakeholders. (3) Small coffee shops in Paranaque City should look into government grants and support initiatives like those offered by the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), the Department of Science and Technology (DOST), and others that can assist business owners in being more efficient and sustainable. Small coffee businesses in Paranaque City ought to attend trade shows, conventions, and exhibitions like the international food expo. To be effective in the performance of their organizations, small coffee shop entrepreneurs must be able to demonstrate their desire for business career accomplishments as well as their self-determination for educational interventions. (4) To develop a strategy

to outperform rivals, small coffee shops in Paranaque City should constantly review and evaluate both their internal and external environments. (5) As with all research, there were certain limitations in the current study. First, the study will only focus on tiny coffee shops in Paranaque City, which might not accurately reflect the variety of coffee shop establishments in other areas or bigger cities. Second, because of its dependence on self-reported data from survey questionnaires, the study may have been biased by responses. Lastly, the research findings could be impacted by outside variables like the state of the economy or shifting customer tastes.

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